

Dawning of a New Dark Age? The G20 Meeting in Hamburg 2017, A Milestone on the Blind Alley towards a Common Global Future

Wolfgang Sassin¹

Wolfgang Sassin,

Dr-Ing,
Independent researcher,
formerly Senior Scientist of International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
and Lecturer of Technical University Vienna
Austria

Вольфганг Зассинь,

докторъ-инженеръ,
независимый изслѣдователь,
въ прошломъ главный научный сотрудникъ
Международного института прикладного системного анализа
и лекторъ Технического университета Вѣны
(Австрія)

Article No and Translation / Номеръ статьи и переводъ: 010110201 ENG

For citation (Chicago style) / Для цитированія (стиль «Чикаго»):

Sassin, Wolfgang. 2020. "Dawning of a new Dark Age? The G20 Meeting in Hamburg 2017, a Milestone on the Blind Alley towards a Common Global Future." *Eur Crossrd* 1, 010110201.

¹ Please send the correspondence to e-mail: w.sassin@aon.at.

Permanent URL links to the article:

HANDLE: 20.500.12656/eurcrossrd.1.010110201

<http://eurcrossrd.ru/pdf/Vol.%201.%20Issue%201.%20010110201%20ENG.pdf>

Received in the original form: 21 April 2020

Review cycles: 2

1st review cycle ready: 16 May 2020

Review outcome: 3 of 3 positive

Decision: To publish with minor revisions

2nd review cycle ready: 22 May 2020

Accepted: 24 May 2020

Published online: 24 May 2020

Translation ready: 26 June 2020

HEADLINE. 2017 G20 Summit in Hamburg: Significance for Eurasia.

ABSTRACT

Wolfgang Sassin. *Dawning of a new Dark Age? The G20 Meeting in Hamburg 2017, a Milestone on the Blind Alley towards a Common Global Future.* The globalisation of mankind as a moral and ethical justification for the installation of a worldwide domestication policy distracts the attention of leading Eurasian politicians from the actual fundamentals and detrimental threats of globalisation in the Eurasian space, especially if economic issues, investment programmes and lending are put in the foreground. These topics can relate to only short-term necessary regulation and control interventions without strategic perspectives of development of Eurasia. Such a narrow understanding of the situation creates a myth that the global expansion of the Western "value system" can continue in Eurasia indefinitely. This basic assumption of the modern "Enlightened" politics of Europeanisation of Eurasia is not just a utopia, a non-existent place like the ancient Greeks thought. It may create a dystopia, the worst place in the world. Will we live in such Eurasia like this?

Key words: globalisation, Eurasia, Europeanisation, G20 in Hamburg, united humanity, one world

On the occasion of the summit of the world's leading industrial nations (G20) in Hamburg 2017, Alpha Conde, the President of the African Union, stated, *“Europe’s fate is interwoven with Africa’s.”* In his interview with the newspaper *Die Welt* on 13 July 2017, he summed up Africa's current political position with this one sentence and concluded, *“We are, so to speak, in the same boat and are threatened with capsizing together. Africa must develop and Europe must understand this.”*

Conde's statements highlight the fundamental transformation that the originally technical term **globalization** has now undergone. It was coined in the last third of the last century with a view to the spread of technological progress and a growing interdependence of national economies through global trade in raw materials and goods (Blowfield 2005; Feenstra 1998; Geiger 2017; Guillen 2001; Kumar 2003). This once and for many still positively occupied idea of human development through exchange across all borders has, however, not led to the hoped-for liberation from poverty and disease, from "cultural backwardness" and a general pacification in the world (Lundsgaarde 2018). Quite the contrary.

Fig. 1. Alpha Conde, the President of the African Union, stated "Europe's fate is interwoven with Africa. We are sitting in the same boat, so to speak, and threaten to capsize together. Africa has to develop and Europe has to understand that."

© www.flickr.com

The concept of **humanity** has undergone a similar subtle transformation. Originally coined in order to distinguish the biological species *homo sapiens* from other members of the hominid species in the image of creation, its meaning initially changed with the founding of the United Nations in 1945 into a kind of family of independent and self-responsible societies, constituted in sovereign nations (Koshy 2000; Weiss et al. 2009; Yost 1966). Their very different problems are now suddenly seen as a task to be solved together and turn the original distinction between humans and animals into a problem community, for many of them even into a liability community (Lynch 2016).

In addition to the stabilization of the fragile world economy and financial markets, the G20 summit focused on geopolitical conflicts, terrorism, uncontrolled migration on a scale previously only seen in world wars, famine and global climate change. According to German Chancellor Angela Merkel in her opening speech entitled “*Shaping a networked world*,” these are crises and challenges, which “*can certainly not be solved by national solitary action, by isolation and protectionism. There will be no return to a world before globalization.*”

Fig. 2. Angela Merkel in her opening speech *Shaping a Networked World* in G20 Summit in Hamburg said, “Shaping Networked World certainly cannot be solved by national solo efforts, isolation and protectionism. There will be no going back to a world before globalization.” This may be understood as a blueprint for united programmatic European Union politics in Eurasia for the nearest years, if the right-wing political groups do not come to power.

Thus nothing less is claimed than to create "the one" common world together. Thinking it through to its logical conclusion, this idea for humanity boils down to a common government, a global social and educational system, de facto to a *Globo*² as the general single currency. This goes hand in hand with the tacit idea that all people would be ready to voluntarily submit to the same living conditions everywhere and for all times.

Expressed in Alpha Conde's language, the credo of the G20, according to the declaration of the German Chancellor, could therefore be summarized as follows: *The fate of every country, every society and every historically developed culture is inextricably linked to the fate of all others. There is no turning back.*

With its implicit values, the G20 summit only made clear what active politicians were and still are committed to if they want to gain and keep an important office. Whether the view of things given by politicians or the goals they set themselves correspond to reality, whether they could at least be implemented in principle, is not clear. A democratically legitimized politician must articulate the interests, hopes and dreams of at least a large part of his or her population and fight for them. If he or she does not do this, he or she will not reach an influential position. This applies to an African like Alpha Conde as well as to all other heads of government who have travelled to Hamburg, regardless of whether they would have met there or elsewhere within the framework of the United Nations.

Not only Conde's statements and observations, therefore, require critical reflection, but those of all summit participants. For they represent intersubjective opinions, a special form of collective convictions that take on very different forms in different societies and that have often enough changed in a revolutionary way in the past. Such "majority opinions," i.e. here *Weltbilder* (world views), are neither carved in stone nor do they have to correspond even approximately to actual conditions. That the world was created in seven days and that man would be destined to be the crown of creation, that the earth would be a flat disc or the center of the Universe, such divided intersubjective opinions appear to us today as archaic myths; quite apart from the various purposes of "man" determined by a superior being.

² Editorial remark:

Here the author implies US dollar as a global currency. He explained in his private correspondence, „Money is the claim to get a real value back. Printing money beyond the volume that is produced and traded in real assets is nothing less than robbery and theft: In such cases real values change their owner without a corresponding compensation by other values. Government bonds purchased by central banks and held as reserve currency are no different from tributes, which are not redeemed. The Bretton Woods system was established in 1944 on the US\$ as the central reserve currency. This is what I mean by GLOBO... In order to facilitate the material exchange between specialized professions, personal debts were anonymized very early on. This required an institution that had to guarantee that these debts were actually paid off in the end. The abolition of debt bondage created a problem that is still unsolved today. This becomes apparent when one compares "currency" in English, i.e. "currency" with the meaning of liquefying trade with the meaning of "Währung" in German. There, „currency“ refers to "always during" and to trust, not to liquefaction and anonymizing of obligations.

Whether in Africa, in Europe or on another continent, a political compromise between the summit participants can neither predict nor determine the future possible or probable development of seven and a half billion people and their now largely artificial livelihood. In most cases, the political ideas that manifest themselves deviate massively from the existing reality. The aim of all politics is precisely to change an unsatisfactory situation, or vice versa, to maintain a desirable situation that is seriously endangered. Politics without competition, without victory of one and defeat of the other is unthinkable (Giorgini 2013; Lukes 2001). Politics necessarily focuses on what is not. It operates in a fictional world and tends to simplify challenges by personalizing them.

The **globalization of humanity** as a moral and ethical justification for the installation of a world domestic policy therefore distracts attention from the actual circumstances, especially when economic issues, investment programs, and the granting of credit are given priority. At best, these issues can only relate to regulatory and control interventions that are necessary in the short term. Such an understanding of the situation tacitly presupposes that the global expansion of the Western "value system" can continue indefinitely and at will. However, precisely this basic assumption of modern "enlightened" politics is not just a utopia, a non-existent place, as the ancient Greeks believed. It is a dystopia, a bad place.

For all serious natural science studies come to the conclusion that "humanity" already today needs one and a half planets, even a multiple of that if the population development in the Third World continues and even more so if there is a significant improvement in the desired and supposedly "ethically required" material standard of living. In such a basic situation, which is not at all disputed by politicians, it is pointless to want to pursue specific problems, to conceive political programs to limit global warming, soil erosion, marine pollution, or the medical and psychological consequences of urbanization. And it is almost absurd to declare in the same moment that further economic growth for social stabilization is inevitable.

In 1992, Francis Fukuyama, in his programmatic work *The End of History*, believed that the end of totalitarian regimes and a peaceful future for the individual in a general liberal democratic order was coming (Fukuyama 2006). What he overlooked then was that the material conditions for a proliferating species would quickly take over the despotic role of authoritarian systems for billions of individuals (Fukuyama 2015; 2018). Today, 25 years later, the world has fallen into a state of disorder. It is "in disarray", as Henry Kissinger puts it. When Fukuyama's book was published, there were two billion fewer people alive than today. This increase in people within just one generation is almost exactly the same as the total number of people who lived before the Second World War. This "partial world", which came into being quasi overnight, could, no wonder, neither bring forth the necessary culture nor a self-sustaining civilization.

If one is considering historical time periods, then we are currently experiencing a rupture that can only be classified as the detonation of a species. The term explosion is not enough. This situation, unprecedented since the appearance of homo sapiens, leads us to an end of all previous "human" history, which is to be understood in a completely different way than

Fukuyama as a political scientist was able to perceive at all. In the extreme slow motion of economists and financial scientists or even sociologists and humanists, the consequences of this "human" detonation are of course not visible in annual balance sheets, in statistics or even in the brains of individual objects of study. It would be as if one wanted to investigate the effect of an explosive device on the still flying metal parts before they hit objects in their environment and profoundly change them and themselves.

In the temporal mode of human generational change, in which knowledge must be passed on and consciousness must always be built up anew, the planet has suddenly changed from an almost unlimited and rich creation into a closed spaceship since the middle of the last century. This spaceship has no "ground station" to supply it with control information and to which it could return if its subsystems should fail or its supplies should run low.

Fig. 3. The G20 Summit in Hamburg was accompanied by unprecedented street protests. Claiming to solve the major issues of humanity, world leaders did not pay any heed to the real challenge before Eurasia: how to limit globalisation and set up a long-term goal to reduce the birth rate to a level of from which a qualitative differentiation and further development of individual parts of humans in Eurasian space are realistic.

© Deutsche Welle; picture-alliance/dpa/M. Scholz

In view of this real situation of "spaceship Earth", the "leading" societies should actually face this epochal challenge and completely redesign the image of man that they have favored up to now. It would have to be adapted to the shortage of human knowledge, skills and assets. After all, we are not just in the midst of an epochal break that may occur once in a hundred or in a thousand years. Contrary to what the green Zeitgeist wants to admit,

man is not simply confronted with a "too scarce" nature, which he has learned to subdue and massively change over the past 300,000 years by developing powerful tools and techniques. Rather, man is suddenly confronted with his own kind, in a density and intensity that has only been seen in extreme exceptional cases in his entire history of development. This new and now quite different environment, which has matured to normality, is formed by its billion-fold existence, behind which "nature" ranks far behind. Hardly anyone can escape this highly complex and artificial environment. And this *Brave New World* can no longer be subdued with even the most sophisticated technology. For such an attempt is always directed against homo sapiens himself.

In the spaceship Earth thus created, there can be neither freedom for further expansion, nor equality with regard to any rights, and of course no competition for control of the planet by plebiscite. Such a "spaceship" would then not only drift randomly and aimlessly through space. It would be doomed to a definite demise, if it should not be possible to match the number and needs of its crew to the available resources, and that means to adapt them to the respective capabilities. Over the past seventy years, humanitarian aid, traditional development aid and the idea of ensuring both through economic growth have led to political confrontations, which have become increasingly heated over the past decade.

But in principle, the political and economic leaders of today's leading Western societies cannot do justice to this central challenge of the 21st century, which has been sketched out very briefly here. Similar to Alpha Conde, they hold their position of power precisely because they are committed to an image of man and a social order which, viewed from a distance, are the actual cause of this precarious spaceship situation.

The three principles of globalization, sustainability and humanity, the latter understood as individual freedom, equality and the pursuit of happiness, codified as universal human rights, "surprisingly" come into conflict with each other because the planet cannot be multiplied. The problem is precisely not a lack of resources, be it oil or gas, agricultural yields or a favorable climate. The problem lies in the competition between the interests of the individual and a community on which the latter has become existentially dependent on a high-level civilization. Both time horizons, that of the individual and that of the artificial civilizational system that supports it, fall further apart the larger and more anonymous a community becomes.

What is, therefore, urgently needed instead of energy policy changes, climate treaties and financial redistribution programs is a fundamental correction of our image of man. This correction can neither be prepared nor enforced by politicians and sociologists, nor by psychologists, nor by inventors and discoverers. Because the spaceship problem cannot be solved technically or administratively. The mental reorientation required for this would amount to nothing less than the establishment of a new mental building providing orientation. It would have to dissociate itself from the tradition of those religions whose images of man developed from the marginal knowledge of the beginning Iron Age about three millennia ago and a planet that was still almost empty until the beginning of the industrial revolution. And it would have to define an unassailable outer framework according to which

everyday events can be classified as right and wrong, "good" and "evil". Religions operate for this purpose with terms like this. What is therefore urgently needed instead of energy policy changes, climate treaties and financial redistribution programs is a fundamental correction of our image of man. This correction can neither be prepared nor enforced by politicians and sociologists, nor by psychologists, nor by inventors and discoverers. Because the spaceship problem cannot be solved technically or administratively. The mental reorientation required for this would amount to nothing less than the establishment of a new mental building providing orientation. It would have to dissociate itself from the tradition of those religions whose images of man developed from the marginal knowledge of the beginning Iron Age about three millennia ago and a planet that was still almost empty until the beginning of the industrial revolution. And it would have to define an unassailable outer framework according to which everyday events can be classified as right and wrong, "good" and "evil." Religions operate for this purpose with terms like *this world and beyond*.

Fig. 4. Almost total inability of the individual to survive even physically in a modern urban world without collective support is probably the deeper reason for the ugly side effects of the Hamburg G20 Summit and other phenomena of violence in the countless human foci in the world, about which the media meanwhile every day to report. It is not difficult to predict how such conditions will spread if Eurasian politics continues to pursue their dystopia of ONE WORLD.

© Deutsche Welle; Getty Images/AFP/S. Loos

It is this lack of a new mental edifice, which has yet to be adopted by a majority, that could dissolve the blatant discrepancy between a *homo deus* promised by politics, as Yuval Noah Harari put it, and the growing number of crises in an intensifying global misery. This

discrepancy can be observed in people who today are neither able to produce a battery themselves nor to describe the functional principles of a smartphone with which they use to arrange protests and violence.

The now almost total inability of the individual to even physically survive in a modern urban world without collective support is probably the deeper reason for the ugly side effects of the Hamburg summit and other phenomena of violence in the countless human hotspots in the world, which the media now report on every day. It is not difficult to predict how such conditions will spread if politics continues to pursue its dystopia of ONE WORLD, in which mega-slums develop into modern, "networked" arks, in which almost half of humanity will soon be crying out for a new Noah.

What lies ahead, and what the G20 Summit, in the tradition of other major political events, has deliberately treated as taboo, is a stringent program to reduce global births and the setting of a long-term goal to reduce the number of homo sapiens to a level from which qualitative differentiation and further development of individual parts of this changing species is a realistic prospect. If it makes any sense at all to speak of One Humanity, it is probably only in the sense of one organism. Such an organism necessarily requires differentiation of its organs. And it demands the meticulous control of all its individual cells. A viable organism can neither grow indefinitely nor allow any proliferation of "autonomous cells" if it does not want to endanger its existence.

The time has come for the representatives of the most important historical edifices of belief, be they spiritual or secular, to sit down together and seek a realistic order for a Universe that was created this time by human beings solely.

As long as this does not happen, all that remains is to set up reservations for civilization, which must be separated from each other by all means. (Sassin et al. 2018; Sassin 2018; 2019a; 2019b; 2020; Donskikh 2019). Human rights of very different kinds would then be limited to those narrow spaces which find their own order within the framework of their respective possibilities and which, to this end, seal themselves off decisively and successfully from the chaos surrounding them.

**Alpha Conde has deciphered the *Mene Tekel* on on the walls of the Temple of Humanists, but missed the first word: "only."
ONLY together you will capsize.**

REFERENCES

- Blowfield, Michael. 2005. "Corporate Social Responsibility: Reinventing the Meaning of Development?" *International Affairs (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944-)* 81, no. 3, Critical Perspectives on Corporate Social Responsibility: 515–524.
- Donskikh, Oleg A. 2019. "Horror Zivilisationis, oder Horror der Subjektivität." *Beacon J Stud Ideol Ment Dimens* 3, no. 1: 020110205.

- <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12656/thebeacon.2.020110205>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3733791>
- Feenstra, Robert C. 1998. "Integration of Trade and Disintegration of Production in the Global Economy." *The Journal of Economic Perspectives* 12, no. 4: 31–50.
- Fukuyama, Francis. 2006. *The End of History and the Last Man*. New York: Free Press.
- Fukuyama, Francis. 2015. *Political Order and Political Decay: From the Industrial Revolution to the Globalization of Democracy*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Fukuyama, Francis. 2018. *Identity: The Demand for Dignity and the Politics of Resentment*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Geiger, Klaus. 2017. „Afrika und Europa drohen gemeinsam zu kentern.“ In *Die Welt*. 13.07.2017.
<https://www.welt.de/politik/ausland/plus166597466/Afrika-und-Europa-drohen-gemeinsam-zu-kentern.html>
- Giorgini, Giovanni. 2013. "Five Hundred Years of Italian Scholarship on Machiavelli's *Prince*." *The Review of Politics* 75, no. 4: 625–640.
- Guillen, Mauro F. 2001. "Is Globalization Civilizing, Destructive or Feeble? A Critique of Five Key Debates in the Social Science Literature." *Annual Review of Sociology* 27: 235–260.
- Koshy, Ninan. 2000. "Sidelining the United Nations." *Economic and Political Weekly* 35, no. 15: 1243–1244.
- Kumar, Vidya S. 2003. "A Critical Methodology of Globalization: Politics of the 21st Century?" *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies* 10, no. 2: 87–111.
- Lukes, Timothy J. 2001. "Lionizing Machiavelli." *The American Political Science Review* 95, no. 3: 561–575.
- Lundsgaarde, Erik. 2018. "Contextualising Globalization Scepticism." In E. Lundsgaarde. *Explaining Globalization Scepticism* (research report). Copenhagen: Danish Institute for International Studies.
- Lynch, Brian. 2016. "The United Nations at 70." *New Zealand International Review* 41, no. 2: 23–26.
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2018. "Die Transformation des sozialen Bewusstseins." *Beacon J Stud Ideol Ment Dimens* 1, no. 1: 010210201.
<https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12656/thebeacon.1.010210201>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3734976>
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2019. "Deja Vue?" *Beacon J Stud Ideol Ment Dimens* 2, no. 2: 020210216.
<https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12656/thebeacon.2.020210216>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3733442>
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2019. "Er-Schöpfung der Schöpfung, oder Eine neue Kulturstufe in der Entwicklung des *homo*." *Beacon J Stud Ideol Ment Dimens* 2, no. 2: 020510203.
<https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12656/thebeacon.2.020510203>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3732508>
- Sassin, Wolfgang. 2020. "Globalisierung und Digitalisierung - Die exponentielle Ausbreitung ansteckender Information und deren mögliche Eindämmung." *Beacon J Stud Ideol Ment*

Dimens 3, no. 1: 010510201.

<https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12656/thebeacon.3.010510201>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3739840>

Sassin, Wolfgang, Donskikh, Oleg, Gnes, Alexandre, Komissarov, Sergei, and Depei Liu.

Evolutionary Environments. Homo Sapiens - an Endangered Species? Innsbruck: Studia Universitätsverlag, 2018.

Weiss, Thomas, Carayannis, Tatiana, and Richard Jolly. 2009. "The "Third" United Nations." *Global Governance* 15, no. 1: 123–142.

Yost, Charles W. 1963. "The United Nations: Crisis of Confidence and Will." *Foreign Affairs* 45, no. 1: 19–35.

EXTENDED SUMMARY

SASSIN, WOLFGANG. DAWNING OF A NEW DARK AGE? THE G20 MEETING IN HAMBURG 2017, A MILESTONE ON THE BLIND ALLEY TOWARDS A COMMON GLOBAL FUTURE.

THE MODERN EURASIA FACES A PRODIGIOUSLY DIFFICULT CHOICE in the wake of its inclusion in the "One World" project. Several additional billion people are to be borne in Eurasia in the nearest several decades, as Eurasian continent has the maximal population growth rate nowadays. Will Eurasia be a true part of the globalised humanity with all perils of globalisation and overpopulation or find its own way where borders mean not the less than borderless spaces, maybe even more?

In the article, we discuss the pivotal point of legitimating Eurasian integration into the global "One World" project, viz. 2017 G20 Summit in Hamburg. During this event, the President of the African Union Alpha Conde formulated the basic principle of such inclusion of Eurasia in the global space, "We are sitting in the same boat, so to speak, and threaten to capsize together." Expressed in Alpha Conde's rhetoric, the G20's credo could be summarised as follows, according to the German Chancellor Angela Merkel's statement: The fate of every country, every society and every historically grown culture is inextricably interwoven with the fate of everyone else. There is no going back.

Almost all G20 Summit participants from Eurasia represented intersubjective opinions, a special form of collective beliefs that take shape in very different ways in different societies and that have changed often enough in the past in a revolutionary way. Such "majority opinions," i.e. "political worldviews," are neither set in stone, nor do they even have to approximate the actual situation. G20 did not address the real hazard to Eurasia in the nearest decades to come and did not do justice to the turbulent beginning of the 21st century that may have taught the leading politicians about mutual threats of globalisation and overpopulation brought together. Most of Eurasian politicians share Angela Merkel's position that we need a networked Eurasia, open inside and outside, whose shaping cannot be solved by national solo efforts, isolation and protectionism, as there can be no going back to a world before globalisation.

Lack of desire to face real Eurasian problems partially led to mass protests in Hamburg and across Europe in June 2017. G20 Summit only clarified what active politicians are working for if they want to seize and hold an important position. It is irrelevant whether the viewpoint given by politicians or the objectives set by them correspond to reality, or whether they could at least be implemented in principle. A “democratically legitimate” Eurasian politician must have interests, hopes and the words of at least a large part of its population in the word and fight for it. If he or she does not do this, he or she will not find him-(her-)self in a precarious position. This applies to an African politician like Alpha Conde as well as to any Eurasian leaders.

The G20 Summit has deliberately treated as taboo topics the real challenges of Eurasian, if not the whole world’s space. In the poorest tradition of many other major political events, G20 participants deliberately overlooked a stringent programme to reduce birth rate, at least in Eurasian space, and set a long-term goal to define a reasonable number of humans in Europe and Eurasia at a level from which a qualitative differentiation and further development are realistic. The nowadays’ almost total inability of an individual to survive even physically in a modern urban world, with Eurasia containing the largest number of urban super-megapolises enormous in size and population (e.g. Shanghai, Bombay, Moscow, Karachi, Jakarta, Dhaka etc.), without collective support, is probably the deeper reason for the ugly side effects of the Hamburg summit and other phenomena of violence in the countless human foci in the world, about which the media are meanwhile to report every day. It is not difficult to predict how such conditions will spread if Eurasian politics continues to pursue their dystopia of “One World” project.

With respect to population, debts, currencies, and *Währungen* (in the sense of a trusted value not just as something that facilitates trade), the Eurasian community must define its position in the world of tomorrow with respect to other world regions that claim the planet as a commons. That may be a hidden concept of the United Nations. This is one of the major issues asking to choose which way to go as Eurasians.

Author / Авторъ

Dr-Ing Wolfgang Sassin’s teaching, research, advisory activities and affiliations included the Technical University of Vienna (Austria), the Research Centre Jülich (Germany), IIASA (Austria), the International Panel on Climate Change IPCC, the UN Program Habitat, the Directorate General on Research and Innovation of the European Commission (Belgium), and OEMs in the German automobile industry on man-machine interfaces.

Wolfgang Sassin,
Independent researcher,
Jochberg 5
6335 Thiersee
Austria

© Wolfgang Sassin
Licensee *Eurasian Crossroads*

Licensing the materials published is made according to Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
International (CC BY 4.0) licence

